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The State of Social Media Research APIs & Tools in the Digital Service Act Era

WHITE PAPER

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This white paper analyzes how the European Union's Digital Services Act (DSA) is transforming data access for platform research, drawing on existing literature and extensive testing of research APIs and tools from major platforms including Meta, YouTube, and TikTok. Our insights are based on years of experience working with social media data and addressing critical data quality issues in platform-provided datasets.

We focus particularly on Article 40.12, which mandates access to "publicly available data," examining how Very Large Online Platforms (VLOPs) are implementing these requirements. The analysis identifies key gaps, challenges, and potential solutions, emphasizing recent developments not yet covered in existing reports.

Key highlights include:

- Critical advancements and challenges in DSA data access, addressing emerging issues and opportunities not yet extensively explored;
- Detailed evaluation of VLOPs' compliance with Article 40.12, including platform-specific analyses of APIs, tools, and data-sharing mechanisms;
- Implementation challenges, including technical constraints, restrictive terms of use, and ambiguities in compliance frameworks;
- Actionable improvements for standardizing data formats, increasing transparency, and expanding researcher accessibility. These recommendations aim to enhance data access usability while fostering a robust research ecosystem.

The white paper concludes by emphasizing the importance of building a strong researcher community to test, evaluate, and improve data access tools. This community will be vital for ensuring tool reliability, advocating for improvements, and fostering collaboration between academia, civil society, and regulatory bodies - ultimately helping realize the DSA's vision of a more transparent and accountable digital ecosystem.

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The DSA and Data Access: A Two-Tiered Approach

The Digital Services Act (DSA) seeks to make online platforms safer and more transparent for users within the EU. A key component of the DSA's strategy is granting researchers access to platform data, which enables them to study and understand systemic risks associated with these platforms. This provision applies to very large online platforms (VLOPs) and very large online search engines (VLOSEs), which serve over 45 million active users in the EU. Systemic risks are defined as potential harms related to "illegal content", "fundamental rights", "civic discourse, electoral processes and public security", and "gender-based violence, the protection of public health, the protection of minors and relating to someone's physical and mental well-being". By providing access to data, the DSA aims to facilitate research that can help mitigate these risks.

The DSA tackles data access through two main avenues:

- Article 40.12, which mandates immediate access to publicly accessible data.
- Article 40.4 (in conjunction with Article 40.8), which outlines a process for researchers to apply for access to non-public data.

The delegated act pertains to Article 40.4 and Article 40.8, as it concerns a more formalized process for accessing non-public data.

Article 40.12: Public Data Access

Article 40.12 is designed to be a relatively straightforward process, granting researchers and non-profit organizations access to data that is already publicly available on the platform's interface. This could include the text of public posts, the number of likes or shares a post receives, or information about public user profiles. The intent is to provide researchers with a baseline understanding of platform dynamics without needing to go through an extensive vetting process.

However, the implementation of Article 40.12 has been somewhat inconsistent across platforms. There is no universally agreed-upon definition of "publicly accessible data," leading to discrepancies in what data platforms make available. Some platforms have created formal programs with application processes, while others simply permit data scraping as a means of access. The lack of standardization has created confusion for researchers and has, in some cases, made it more difficult to obtain the data needed for their research.

Delegated Act Access (Article 40.4 and 40.8): Non-Public Data Access

The delegated act access, governed by Articles 40.4 and 40.8, deals with requests for non-public data, which may contain sensitive information. This access route requires a more rigorous vetting process to protect user privacy and ensure data security. The key distinctions of this access pathway are:

- Vetted Researchers: Access is restricted to "vetted researchers," who must meet specific criteria and undergo a more thorough review process. While the specific criteria are still being defined, it will likely involve assessing the researcher's qualifications, the legitimacy of their research organization, and the robustness of their data protection plans.
- Systemic Risk Focus: Research projects must clearly demonstrate their focus on studying and understanding systemic risks within the EU. Applications will likely need to articulate the specific risks being investigated and how the requested non-public data is essential to addressing those risks.
- Proportionality and Justification: The requested data must be "proportionate" to the research objectives, and researchers must provide strong justifications for why they need access to sensitive information. The goal is to strike a balance between enabling valuable research and safeguarding user privacy.
- Regulatory Oversight: Unlike Article 40.12, where platforms largely manage the process of data access, access to non-public data involves a significant level of regulatory oversight. The delegated act will outline procedures for submitting data requests to Digital Services Coordinators (DSCs), who will then consult with an independent intermediary body to assess the merits of the request before making a decision.

This process for accessing non-public data is still under development. The delegated act is expected to provide greater clarity on the application process, eligibility criteria, and data-sharing frameworks.

The European Commission has recently advanced the implementation of Article 40 of the DSA to study systemic risks within the EU. A draft delegated act detailing the specific conditions and procedures for such data access was published for consultation on October 31, 2024.

The consultation period for the draft delegated act concluded on December 10, 2024, gathering 109 valid feedback submissions¹ from a diverse range of stakeholders, including academic institutions, NGOs, social media companies, and industry associations. Notably, the participation of several social media companies underscores their vested interest in the regulatory framework. The contributions also highlight significant international engagement, with responses received from stakeholders across 18 countries. These insights will inform the Commission's efforts to adopt the final rules in the first quarter of 2025, providing comprehensive guidance on the application process, eligibility criteria, and data-sharing frameworks for non-public data under Article 40 of the Digital Services Act.

The Evolving Landscape of Data Access

The DSA is prompting a shift in how social media platforms handle data access for research purposes. While some platforms have restricted access in recent years, citing concerns about privacy and monetization of data, the DSA has mounted pressure on the platforms to develop more robust data-sharing programs.

¹ For detailed data on the feedback submissions, visit the official consultation page: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13817-Delegated-Regulation-on-data-access-provided-for-in-the-Digital-Services-Act/feedback_it?p_id=33193431

However, the implementation of the DSA's data access provisions is an ongoing process. Many platforms are still working to establish their programs and refine their procedures. Researchers, regulators, and platforms are actively engaged in discussions and evaluations to shape the future of data access under the DSA.

Staying informed about the latest developments in data access is essential for advancing research and contributing to ongoing conversations. Researchers can play a pivotal role by actively engaging with existing data access programs to evaluate their strengths and limitations. By documenting and reporting challenges encountered during the application process or data usage, researchers can help identify areas where improvements are needed. Additionally, sharing best practices and fostering collaboration with other scholars is crucial for building a collective understanding of how to effectively leverage these new data access opportunities. This collaborative approach ensures that researchers can maximize the benefits of emerging data-sharing frameworks while driving further enhancements in accessibility and usability.

By working together, researchers, platforms, and regulators can create a more transparent and accountable digital environment that benefits both users and society as a whole.

Assessing DSA Article 40.12 Compliance

The objective of the white paper is to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of social media research APIs and tools through the lens of Article 40.12 of the DSA. This entails a detailed assessment of how well social media platforms are complying with the DSA's mandate to provide researchers with access to publicly accessible data.

- Focus on Article 40.12: The white paper will specifically concentrate on Article 40.12 of the DSA, which deals with access to publicly available data, as opposed to the more complex process of requesting non-public data under Articles 40.4 and 40.8.
- Evaluation of Data Accessibility: The white paper will evaluate the types of data that platforms make available through their APIs and tools. It will consider factors such as:
 - The scope of data offered, including whether it covers a wide range of content types, user demographics, and engagement metrics.
 - Whether live data (real-time or near-real time) or random samples of platform content can be acquired.
 - The search capabilities of the APIs, including the availability of filters and the ability to query data in a granular way.
- Assessment of API Usability: The white paper will also assess the usability of the APIs and tools themselves, taking into account aspects like:
 - The clarity and comprehensiveness of documentation provided to researchers.
 - The ease of use of the APIs, particularly for researchers who may not have extensive technical expertise.
 - The presence of any technical limitations, such as rate limits or restrictions on the amount of data that can be requested, and how these limitations impact research.

- **Analysis of Transparency and Consistency:** The white paper will analyze the transparency of platforms in communicating their data access policies and procedures to researchers. It will also examine the consistency of data access across different platforms and whether there are significant discrepancies in how platforms interpret and implement Article 40.12.
- **Exploration of Challenges and Recommendations:** The white paper will explore the challenges researchers face in accessing and utilizing platform data under Article 40.12. Based on this analysis, it will offer recommendations for improvements to data access programs, including:
 - Suggestions for creating more standardized definitions of "publicly accessible data" to ensure greater consistency across platforms.
 - Recommendations for improving the clarity and accessibility of documentation to make it easier for researchers to use the APIs effectively.
 - Proposals for developing tools that cater to researchers with varying levels of technical expertise, such as dashboards or downloadable datasets for non-programmatic analysis.
 - Ideas for establishing mechanisms to ensure the quality and reliability of data provided through APIs, potentially through independent audits or verification processes.

By providing a comprehensive overview of the current state of social media research APIs and tools in light of Article 40.12, the white paper will aim to contribute to a more informed discussion about the DSA's implementation and its impact on research.

Key Concepts and Definitions

Digital Services Act (DSA): The Digital Services Act (DSA) is a piece of EU legislation designed to enhance online safety and transparency for users in the EU. A cornerstone of the DSA is its mandate for social media platforms, particularly Very Large Online Platforms (VLOPs) and Very Large Online Search Engines (VLOSEs), to grant researchers access to data for the purpose of studying systemic risks. The DSA outlines two pathways for data access:

- Article 40(12): This article focuses on providing researchers with access to publicly accessible data.
- Article 40(4)(in conjunction with Article 40(8)): This pathway establishes a more stringent process for "vetted" researchers to apply for access to non-public data.

Systemic Risks: Systemic risks, in the context of the DSA, refer to potential negative consequences stemming from the design and operation of online platforms and search engines that impact society at a large scale. These risks can arise from various factors, including: the dissemination of illegal content, negative effects on fundamental rights, negative effects on civic discourse and electoral processes, threats to public security, and negative effects on public health and well-being.

Data Access Approaches:

- **Application Programming Interfaces (APIs):** An API (Application Programming Interface) serves as a digital bridge between researchers and social media platforms, enabling programmatic access to platform data. Using programming languages like R or Python, researchers can send

structured queries to these APIs, which then act as intermediaries to fetch specific data from the platform's backend systems. For instance, a researcher studying hate speech could use an API to retrieve posts containing particular keywords, filtered by date range and engagement metrics. The API processes these requests and returns the data in a structured format that researchers can analyze.

- **Scraping:** Web scraping is an automated data collection method where researchers use specialized code or tools to extract information directly from websites. The process involves writing scripts that navigate web pages like a human user would, analyzing the HTML structure to locate and collect specific data points. These scripts systematically parse through web pages' source code to gather the desired information in a structured format for analysis.
- **Dashboards:** Dashboards serve as user-friendly visual interfaces that enable researchers to explore social media data without programming expertise. These interactive tools provide intuitive ways to filter, sort, and visualize data trends through charts, graphs, and tables. Researchers can dynamically adjust parameters and explore different aspects of the underlying datasets by interacting with dashboard controls, making complex data analysis more accessible to non-technical users.
- **Downloadable Datasets:** Downloadable datasets are curated collections of social media data that platforms compile and make available for offline analysis. Typically provided in accessible formats like CSV files, these pre-assembled datasets allow researchers to analyze platform data using familiar tools such as spreadsheet software or statistical packages. Platforms may create these collections based on specific criteria or in response to research requests, offering a straightforward way for researchers to access and study platform data without requiring real-time API access.

Important Considerations:

- **Rate Limits/Quotas:** Rate limits, also known as quotas, are restrictions imposed by APIs and websites that limit the number of data requests a researcher can make within a specific timeframe. These limits can significantly impact research, particularly for large-scale studies that require access to extensive datasets. Most platforms with research APIs implement rate limits to prevent server overload and ensure fair access for all users.
- **Documentation and Supplementary Data:** Documentation for research APIs and tools must be clear, comprehensive, and publicly accessible, going beyond basic endpoint listings to provide researchers with essential insights. By providing this depth of information, platforms enable researchers to effectively utilize their tools while ensuring responsible data handling and compliance with platform policies.
- **Types and Formats of Social Media Expression:** Social media platforms offer researchers diverse data types across three main categories: textual, multimedia, and user data. Textual data includes posts, comments, captions, and hashtags, which reveal trends, public opinion, and communication patterns. Multimedia content encompasses images, videos, live streams, and ephemeral stories, offering insights into visual communication and online culture. User data provides information through public profiles, demographic details (when available), follower relationships, and engagement metrics like likes and shares.

Overview of Data Access Approaches

Platforms have adopted various strategies to comply with the DSA and provide researchers with access to data. These range from formal research programs and adapted APIs to data scraping permissions and direct data request mechanisms, each presenting unique benefits and challenges for effective research.

Formal Research Programs under Article 40(12)

In response to Article 40(12) of the Digital Services Act (DSA), several platforms, including AliExpress, Google Search, Meta (Facebook and Instagram), TikTok, and LinkedIn, have established formal research programs to provide researchers with access to publicly available data. While these programs share common features—such as application procedures, eligibility criteria, and terms of service—they vary significantly in data access methods, provisions, and overall quality.

Most programs require researchers to submit detailed applications that outline their research project, institutional affiliation, and data protection plans. Eligibility criteria are generally focused on non-commercial research purposes, with a preference for academic institutions or researchers investigating systemic risks within the EU. Data access methods differ widely, ranging from APIs and interactive dashboards to downloadable datasets and permission to scrape publicly available data. The level of documentation and support also varies, making it difficult for researchers to compare data across platforms and perform comprehensive analyses, particularly when information about data availability and formatting is limited.

Researchers have expressed concerns about lengthy application processes and restrictive terms of service, such as pre-publication review requirements, which can hinder research independence. Data quality issues, including inconsistencies between API-retrieved data and data visible on platform interfaces, further complicate research efforts. These challenges underscore the need for standardized guidelines and independent auditing mechanisms to ensure data accuracy and reliability.

On the other hand, platforms face the challenge of balancing researchers' data access needs with user privacy and security concerns, as well as managing the administrative workload associated with these programs. Despite these obstacles, formal research programs are valuable tools for studying systemic risks and enhancing platform accountability. Greater data access can lead to a deeper understanding of online harms and more informed policy-making. By addressing these challenges and expanding data access provisions, these programs have the potential to become even more valuable resources for researchers, platforms, and society as a whole.

Existing APIs and Data Access Programs

To comply with Article 40(12) of the DSA, several platforms have opted to adapt their existing APIs and data access programs. This approach allows them to provide researchers with structured access to data, leveraging already established systems. Notable examples include Bing, Wikipedia, X (formerly Twitter), and YouTube.

Bing offers access to a variety of tools through its Qualified Researcher Program, including the Bing Search API, Bing Webmaster Tools, and specific datasets². These resources provide data related to search activity, website performance, and more, supporting research on search engine dynamics and visibility.

Wikipedia, as an open-access resource, already makes its data widely available. Researchers can access content in multiple formats via the Wikipedia API Parsed Infobox³, Wikimedia Downloads⁴, and Wikipedia Page History⁵, facilitating research on content evolution and public information dissemination.

X (formerly Twitter) has made its commercial API accessible to researchers studying DSA-related topics⁶, although it remains a paid service for other users. Researchers who qualify can obtain data crucial for understanding information spread and communication dynamics on the platform.

YouTube provides academic researchers with access to its Data API through its Researcher Program⁷, allowing them to retrieve public video metadata. The program also includes limited scraping permissions for DSA-eligible research projects, enabling deeper analysis of content trends and engagement patterns.

Suitability of Pre-Existing Data Access Mechanisms for Research

The effectiveness of these existing mechanisms for research purposes depends on several factors, including data coverage, rate limits, and the quality of provided documentation.

Data Coverage

The scope of available data varies across platforms. YouTube's Data API grants researchers access to extensive public video metadata, suitable for analyzing content dynamics. Bing provides a range of data on search behaviors and website performance. Wikipedia offers comprehensive access to its entire content and revision history, supporting longitudinal studies. However, X restricts its data access to a narrower subset focused on DSA-related research, and the variety of data available from other platforms' APIs can differ significantly, complicating research efforts⁸.

Rate Limits

Restrictions on data usage present another challenge. YouTube imposes a daily quota of 10,000 units, though researchers can apply for extensions if necessary⁹. X enforces specific limits even for DSA-related

² See

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/topic/bing-qualified-researcher-program-b1c5a4b6-3ad6-4c8c-963d-a395c7766c85>

³ See <https://enterprise.wikimedia.com/blog/structured-contents-wikipedia-infobox/>

⁴ See <https://dumps.wikimedia.org/>

⁵ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Help:Page_history

⁶ As stated at: <https://developer.x.com/en/use-cases/do-research>

⁷ See <https://research.youtube/>

⁸ X states that the application for Research under EU Digital Services Act «is only for a narrow subset of EU research related to the DSA. For general academic research, please enroll in one of our X API access tiers». See:

<https://developer.x.com/en/use-cases/do-research>

⁹ See <https://developers.google.com/youtube/v3/getting-started>

research, which may restrict large-scale data collection¹⁰. Platforms like Reddit and Google reserve the right to impose rate limits as needed, creating potential barriers to extensive research¹¹. The specific rate limits for Bing's Qualified Researcher Program remain unclear in available resources.

Documentation Quality

The quality and clarity of documentation also impact research utility. YouTube provides extensive guidelines on data use, API functions, and quota management, while Wikipedia offers detailed documentation for its data access tools. Conversely, X's documentation for DSA-related research lacks specificity, which may hinder effective use. The documentation quality for Bing's research program is not well-documented in the sources.

Challenges and Limitations of Existing Data Access Mechanisms

While pre-existing data access mechanisms offer cost-effective compliance with the DSA, they present significant limitations for researchers. Platforms like YouTube often prioritize academic institutions, excluding civil society organizations and journalists, which restricts research diversity and limits insights into systemic risks and societal impacts.

The ambiguity around the definition of "publicly accessible data" leads to inconsistent data availability and complicates essential cross-platform comparisons. Lengthy and complex application processes further exacerbate these challenges, requiring extensive documentation and often resulting in prolonged approval times, which hinder time-sensitive studies.

Data discrepancies between APIs and platform interfaces also pose issues, undermining research accuracy and highlighting the need for independent audits to ensure data reliability. Despite these challenges, leveraging existing mechanisms remains practical for DSA compliance. However, to be truly effective, platforms must address these limitations, refine data access frameworks, and improve transparency and documentation, thereby enhancing research capabilities, accountability, and policy discussions.

¹⁰ The X DSA Researcher Application form (<https://forms.gle/btDwenPF7M3hgSvw7>) requires detailed justification for the scope of data, timeframe, and purpose, aligning access strictly with Article 34(1) of the DSA. Furthermore, the X Developer Agreement (see: <https://developer.x.com/en/developer-terms/agreement>) explicitly prohibits attempts to exceed or circumvent API limitations ("Rate Limits") or engage in excessive usage, with violations resulting in suspension or permanent blocking of access. These combined measures impose significant constraints on the feasibility of large-scale data collection.

¹¹ Reddit states that it "may set and enforce limits on your use of the Data APIs (e.g., limiting the number of API requests that you may make or the number of App Users you may serve), in our sole discretion" (see: <https://redditinc.com/policies/data-api-terms>). See also similar language in Google's Researcher Program Acceptable Use Policy, available at Google Request Records: "Your use of Program Access and Program Data is subject to your agreement to abide by the technical limitations (e.g., rate limits) and security requirements for each Google service you access. These technical and security limitations may evolve over the course of the program, and will be provided to you upon successful admittance into the program, where these requirements are applicable. They will at no time prohibit the publication of findings and methodology from research undertaken in the context of this program." (see: <https://requestrecords.google.com/researcher/policy>)

Scraping and Data Collection

Data scraping has become a common method for researchers to access publicly available information on digital platforms. Some companies, like Alphabet, explicitly allow “limited scraping” for services such as Google Search, Play Store, Shopping, and YouTube. Others, including Booking.com, Amazon, and Pinterest, implicitly permit non-commercial scraping through their terms of service, making it a viable yet complex tool for academic research.

Legal and Ethical Considerations

While scraping public data is often viewed as lawful (or in some cases tolerated, including by EU regulators¹²) researchers must be mindful of platforms’ terms of service, which frequently prohibit scraping to manage server load, protect user privacy, or safeguard financial interests. Additionally, legal issues such as copyright infringement may arise if the scraped content is protected. Researchers must ensure that their activities align with relevant copyright laws and platform rules. Privacy concerns are also paramount, especially when scraping involves personal data. Compliance with privacy regulations, such as the GDPR, and respect for user privacy expectations are critical.

Technical Challenges

Scraping presents various technical hurdles. Despite the legal and ethical considerations, scraping may be still seen by the platforms as an adversarial approach activity to be blocked or limited. Automated tools, from basic scripts to complex software, are needed to extract data from sites that may employ anti-scraping measures. The maintenance of scraping custom code and access tools is thus time-consuming and prone to reliability issues. Post-extraction, the data often requires extensive cleaning and processing to eliminate noise, standardize formats, and ensure usability and accuracy. These steps can be resource-intensive, but are necessary for maintaining the integrity of the research data.

Independent Audits and Verification

Discrepancies between API data and the information displayed on platforms have highlighted the need for independent audits and verification processes. These mechanisms are essential for validating the accuracy and reliability of scraped data. Audits can identify biases or inconsistencies, offering platforms constructive feedback to enhance data quality and transparency, ultimately benefiting both researchers and the broader digital research community.

Data Requests and Ad Hoc Access

Certain platforms, such as Apple’s App Store and Snapchat, have adopted data request mechanisms as their primary method for granting researchers access to publicly accessible data. These platforms typically offer an

¹² For example, the European Digital Media Observatory notes public statements made by the EC that the interpretation of Art. 40(12) appears to enable non-permissioned scraping. See <https://edmo.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Report-on-EDMO-Workshop-on-Platform-Data-Access-for-Researchers.pdf>

email address or contact form for submissions¹³. However, these mechanisms are often plagued by a lack of standardized procedures and insufficient documentation, leaving researchers with minimal guidance on what data is available, its format, the application review process, or expected response times. This lack of transparency complicates research planning and increases the risk of unforeseen obstacles.

The absence of clear standards introduces several difficulties for researchers. One major issue is uncertainty regarding data availability. Without detailed information on the types of data platforms collect and make accessible, researchers may struggle to formulate precise research questions and design studies effectively. Another significant challenge is variable response times, which can delay projects and disrupt funding timelines, creating difficulties in maintaining a consistent research schedule. Additionally, inconsistent data formats necessitate extra time and effort for data cleaning and processing, complicating analysis and hindering cross-platform comparisons.

Need for improved transparency and standardization

The lack of transparency and standardization in data request mechanisms hampers research on systemic online risks and limits the potential for meaningful academic contributions. Addressing these issues requires implementing several key improvements:

- **clear definition of “public data”:** regulators should formalize a definition of “public data” to ensure consistency in data access provisions and eliminate ambiguity for researchers;
- **standardized application procedures:** platforms should establish uniform application processes that inform researchers about data availability, request formats, review timelines, and response expectations;
- **documentation of data formats:** comprehensive documentation on data formats should be provided, enabling researchers to anticipate processing requirements and streamline their analysis;
- **service level agreements:** platforms could implement service level agreements specifying response times, giving researchers greater predictability and helping them adhere to project schedules.

By adopting these measures, platforms can significantly improve the transparency and efficiency of their data request systems, facilitating more robust research into systemic risks and enhancing our collective understanding of online platforms’ societal impact.

Platform-Specific Analysis

The following entities are Very Large Online Platforms (VLOPs) and/or Very Large Online Search Engines (VLOSEs) subject to obligations under Article 40 of the EU's DSA: These platforms are subject to certain

¹³ For example, Apple DSA Compliance for the App Store, and DSA-Researcher-Access[at]snapchat.com for Snapchat

obligations under the DSA, including sharing publicly accessible data with researchers studying "systemic risks to the European Union".

AliExpress¹⁴

AliExpress offers a Dataworks API and datasets through its Open Research and Transparency portal for approved researchers affiliated with academic institutions and nonprofit organizations in the EU. The portal provides access to "privacy protected datasets and other statistical data" within a controlled environment. There is no mention of specific API endpoints, the types of data they offer, rate limits, or any other specific details about the data provided. Researchers cannot export the data from the "internal network-based controlled access environment". Documentation regarding the application process and what data is offered is very limited. AliExpress did not respond to requests for comment or further discussion.

Amazon Store

While Amazon Store does not provide a formal data access program, the company has indicated through official communications that researchers complying with the DSA are permitted to use industry-standard research tools to collect publicly available data from Amazon's EU store, specifically for purposes outlined in Article 40(12) of the DSA. However, the practical feasibility of such data collection remains unclear due to the presence of anti-scraping systems that may impede automated data gathering efforts.

Apple's App Store

While Apple's App Store lacks a formal data access program or API, the company's DSA Compliance team has indicated that procedures exist for researchers to request publicly available App Store data in compliance with Article 40(12) of the DSA. Researchers are directed to contact Apple DSA Compliance for such requests. However, the process remains largely opaque, with no clear documentation regarding data formats, request procedures, scope of available data, or potential limitations. The absence of a well-documented program and lack of evidence of successful researcher access makes it difficult to evaluate the practical viability of obtaining App Store data for research purposes.

Bing¹⁵

Bing provides research access through its Qualified Researcher Program, specifically designed for independent researchers studying systemic risks in the European Union under the DSA framework. The program offers multiple data access points, including the Bing Search API for query and results data, Bing Webmaster Tools for website performance insights, and specialized datasets covering topics like misinformation and social trends. While the program features high-quality documentation and a clear application process, it has notable limitations, including a narrow EU-centric focus, unclear selection

¹⁴ Official documentation at: <https://yida.alibaba-inc.com/o/research/api#/>

¹⁵ Official documentation at:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/topic/bing-qualified-researcher-program-b1c5a4b6-3ad6-4c8c-963d-a395c7766c85>

criteria, and limited transparency regarding data content and formats. Though there are no specified short-term rate limits, researchers must justify their data requests, and long-term restrictions may apply. Interested researchers can access the application form and documentation through Microsoft's support website.

Booking.com¹⁶

Booking.com does not offer a formal program for researcher data access. However, Booking.com's customer terms of service state that scraping is permissible for non-commercial purposes. As researchers qualifying for data access under Article 40.12 of the Digital Services Act must be independent of commercial interests, they are likely permitted to scrape the platform. Booking.com does provide a Researchers Data Request Portal where researchers can apply for access to public data. It is not clear in what format this data will be provided.

Facebook¹⁷

Meta provides researchers with access to public data from Facebook, Instagram, and Threads through the Meta Content Library and its API. These tools offer both a web-based interface and programmatic access for querying public content. The Content Library includes public posts from Facebook Pages, groups, events, and profiles with a verified badge or 1,000 or more followers. Meta has introduced a feature that allows researchers to download certain publicly accessible content posted by widely known individuals and organizations as CSV files through the Meta Content Library user interface. This enhancement aims to facilitate easier access to data for research purposes. However, it's important to note that this feature is subject to specific eligibility criteria and may not encompass all public content. Researchers should consult Meta's official documentation for detailed information on the availability and scope of downloadable data.

The API extends this access, allowing for more detailed queries and data analysis. Meta offers comprehensive documentation and data dictionaries to assist researchers. However, there are limitations, including rate restrictions of 60 requests per minute and a rolling seven-day cap of 500,000 results for combined use of the Content Library and API. Additionally, the discontinuation of CrowdTangle in August 2024 has removed certain features, such as time-series data access and collaborative research tools, which were particularly valuable during election periods.

Google Maps¹⁸

Google Maps provides researchers with comprehensive data access through multiple channels, including various APIs (Places, Geocoding, Maps JavaScript, and Directions), the Google Cloud Console dashboard, and Google Request Records for limited scraping. The platform offers excellent documentation through the Google Maps Platform Documentation website, complete with detailed guides, tutorials, and reference materials. Available data includes demographic information, user engagement metrics like

¹⁶ Official documentation at: <https://www.booking.com/content/terms.html>

¹⁷ Official documentation at: <https://transparency.fb.com/researchtools/meta-content-library>

¹⁸ Official documentation at: <https://requestrecords.google.com/researcher>

ratings and reviews, and content metadata. While the platform maintains specific rate limits (such as 100,000 daily requests for the Places API), it generally offers fewer access restrictions compared to other platforms. The service could further enhance its research support by introducing thematic datasets and providing clearer guidelines for data scraping permissions.

Google Play¹⁹

Google Play offers researchers multiple data access options, including the Google Play Developer API for app information and user reviews, and the Google Play Console for performance metrics and engagement statistics. For EU researchers, the Google Researcher Program provides additional access through "limited scraping" permissions. The platform's documentation is well-maintained, particularly for the Developer API, which allows up to 200,000 queries per day. Available data includes app performance metrics, user engagement statistics, and financial information. While the platform provides these various access points, there's limited transparency regarding the Google Researcher Program's specific scope and limitations. The platform could enhance its research support by offering clearer documentation about scraping permissions and introducing thematic datasets.

Google Search²⁰

Google Search provides limited research data access options, primarily through the Search Researcher Result API (SRR API), which allows EU researchers to access search results in HTML format with a daily limit of 1,000 queries per project. While the platform permits "limited scraping" and data requests, specific details about these processes are unclear. The platform faces several challenges, including poor documentation, unclear eligibility criteria, and limited tools for non-technical researchers. Key recommendations for improvement include providing clearer documentation about data access programs, increasing support for researcher applications, developing tools for non-technical users, standardizing data schemas across platforms, establishing data quality standards, and implementing a more flexible rate limit system. Notably, Google only retains Search data for one year, and monitoring of API usage is available through the Google Cloud Console.

Google Shopping²¹

Google Shopping provides research data access through multiple channels, including the Content API for Shopping for product listings and pricing data, and the Merchant Center dashboard for performance metrics. EU researchers can additionally access data through the Google Researcher Program's "limited scraping" permission. The platform maintains comprehensive documentation for its Content API, offering extensive tutorials and guides. Available data includes product performance metrics, inventory levels, and pricing trends. While rate limits vary by account type, higher quotas can be requested. However, the platform faces common challenges including unclear eligibility criteria, limited tools for non-technical researchers, and ambiguous data availability information. Recommendations for improvement include

¹⁹ Official documentation at: <https://requestrecords.google.com/researcher>

²⁰ Official documentation at: <https://requestrecords.google.com/researcher>

²¹ Official documentation at: <https://requestrecords.google.com/researcher>

enhancing program discoverability, clarifying access requirements, developing non-technical tools, standardizing data schemas, and implementing better data validation mechanisms.

Instagram²²

Researchers can access Instagram data through Meta's Content Library and the Content Library API, which provide both dashboard and programmatic interfaces for querying public content. The available data includes public account information (follower counts, following counts, biographical data) and post metrics (likes, comments, views, creation dates, media types, hashtags). Meta provides detailed documentation and data dictionaries to support researchers. The platform enforces rate limits of 60 requests per minute and a rolling seven-day cap of 500,000 results for the combined use of the Content Library and API. Meta has introduced a feature that allows researchers to download certain publicly accessible content posted by widely known individuals and organizations as CSV files through the Meta Content Library user interface. This enhancement aims to facilitate easier access to data for research purposes. However, it's important to note that this feature is subject to specific eligibility criteria and may not encompass all public content. Researchers should consult Meta's official documentation for detailed information on the availability and scope of downloadable data. Challenges include discoverability issues, unclear eligibility criteria, variable data availability, and limited user-friendly tools for non-technical users. Recommendations for improvement include enhancing program visibility, clarifying access requirements, improving documentation, developing intuitive analysis tools, standardizing cross-platform data schemas, enforcing data quality standards, and implementing more flexible rate limit

LinkedIn²³

LinkedIn's research data access is primarily offered through its beta Researcher Access Program, launched in August 2023 to comply with the EU's Digital Services Act (DSA). While the program promises qualified researchers access to publicly available platform data, significant details remain unclear, including data delivery formats, available endpoints, documentation quality, supplementary data types, and rate limitations. Currently, LinkedIn restricts research access to this program exclusively, not supporting other research project requests related to their public data. While data scraping might be technically possible, it's generally discouraged due to reliability issues, platform anti-automation measures, and potential terms of service violations. The program's lack of transparency about its operational specifics, including API endpoints, data dictionaries, codebooks, and volume restrictions, makes it difficult for researchers to fully understand and evaluate its research capabilities, suggesting a need for more detailed documentation and clearer access protocols.

Pinterest²⁴

Pinterest provides research data access through a global application program, notably accommodating scraping requests from DSA Article 40(12) qualified researchers, indicating flexibility in data delivery formats. The application process requires detailed information about the researcher's organization and

²² Official documentation at: <https://transparency.fb.com/researchtools/meta-content-library>

²³ Official documentation at: <https://www.linkedin.com/help/linkedin/answer/a1645616?>

²⁴ Official documentation at: <https://help.pinterest.com/en/landing/researchers-intake-form>

project, including non-profit status, research location, commercial independence, and confirmation that the data will be used specifically for studying systemic risks in the EU. However, the platform provides limited public information about crucial program aspects, including available endpoints, documentation quality, data dictionaries, supplementary data types, and both short-term and long-term volume restrictions. This approach, similar to LinkedIn's, suggests Pinterest is in the early stages of developing its research data access program, prioritizing compliance with DSA requirements while maintaining flexibility in program implementation. The lack of specific details about data formats, documentation, and rate limits indicates a cautious approach as the platform gains experience with researcher requests.

Snapchat²⁵

Snapchat offers a DSA-compliant research data access program, accepting email requests from researchers with non-commercial purposes who wish to access public platform data. The application process requires detailed information including the researcher's name, organizational affiliation, research focus, intended data use, and security and retention protocols, with approved requests receiving data in CSV format. However, the program appears to be in its nascent stages, with no researchers having utilized it as of May 2024. The platform provides minimal public information about crucial aspects such as available endpoints, documentation quality, data dictionaries, supplementary data types, or volume restrictions. Snapchat's approach emphasizes individualized review of research requests rather than standardized API access, though this case-by-case methodology, combined with limited transparency about program specifics, may create challenges for researchers trying to evaluate the program's suitability for their research needs.

TikTok²⁶

TikTok provides research access through its Research API, available to eligible researchers in the U.S. and Europe, offering two main endpoints: `/video/query` for content searches based on various criteria, and `/user/info` for account information retrieval. The API provides comprehensive data including user profiles (display names, bios, verification status, follower counts), content information (video details, creation times, regional codes, hashtags), and engagement metrics (likes, comments, shares, views). However, the platform faces significant challenges: a restrictive rate limit of 1,000 requests daily (maximum 100,000 records), approximately 10-day data delays, documented accuracy issues (particularly for pre-July 2024 metadata and engagement metrics), limited variable availability, unclear documentation (especially regarding search queries), and burdensome user agreement terms. Despite these limitations, the API represents a notable effort toward platform transparency, though improvements in data accuracy, documentation clarity, and update communication are needed to enhance its research utility. The platform provides a codebook detailing data structures and formats, enabling research on platform dynamics, misinformation, and online harms.

²⁵ Official documentation at: <https://values.snap.com/privacy/transparency/researcher-access>

²⁶ Official documentation at: <https://developers.tiktok.com/products/research-api/>

Wikipedia²⁷

Wikipedia stands out among platforms by offering unrestricted research access to its data without requiring formal applications or approvals. The platform provides multiple data access methods: comprehensive APIs with detailed documentation for programmatic interaction, explicit permission for data scraping, downloadable datasets from the Wikimedia Foundation, and built-in exploratory tools within the platform itself. The documentation ecosystem includes clear terms of use for content licensing and attribution, extensive API guidelines covering usage etiquette and robot protocols, and research-specific FAQs. While specific rate limits aren't explicitly detailed, Wikipedia's commitment to open data suggests a permissive approach to data volume. This open accessibility model, supported by comprehensive documentation and multiple access methods, makes Wikipedia an invaluable resource for researchers studying online knowledge production, collaborative content creation, and information dissemination patterns, though researchers are expected to follow platform guidelines for responsible data collection.

X (formerly Twitter)²⁸

X's (formerly Twitter) research data accessibility has undergone significant transformation since its acquisition by Elon Musk, shifting from an open API model to a predominantly commercial structure. The platform now offers tiered API access, with varying levels of data availability and rate limits based on subscription level, alongside a specialized application process for DSA-related research in the EU. Through these channels, researchers can access diverse data types including tweets, user profiles, timelines, direct messages, lists, trends, and media, supplemented by engagement metrics, timestamps, geolocation data, and user demographics. The platform maintains comprehensive documentation, including detailed API guides, data dictionaries, and codebooks explaining data structures and formats. However, the platform's commercialization of API access has raised significant concerns within the research community, particularly regarding the accessibility of data for smaller research projects or those lacking funding for paid tiers.

YouTube²⁹

YouTube provides multiple data access pathways for researchers, primarily through its Data API v3, which offers endpoints for videos, comments, playlists, channel information, and content moderation actions. Additional access options include YouTube Analytics for channel-specific metrics and a Higher Education Program offering expanded API access for approved academics. The platform maintains excellent documentation quality, including comprehensive guides, tutorials, data dictionaries, and codebooks, allowing researchers to access various supplementary data such as performance metrics, audience demographics, and content metadata. However, significant limitations exist, particularly in the API's quota system: the default 10,000 units per day becomes restrictive due to search requests consuming 100 units for just 10 videos, effectively limiting researchers to 100 searches daily. While data scraping is

²⁷ Official documentation at: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Tools>

²⁸ Official documentation at: <https://developer.twitter.com/en/use-cases/do-research/>

²⁹ Official documentation at: <https://requestrecords.google.com/researcher>

technically possible, it's discouraged through terms of service restrictions and anti-automation measures.

Zalando

Zalando, despite its status as a Very Large Online Platform (VLOP) under the EU's Digital Services Act (DSA), maintains minimal transparency regarding its research data accessibility. The platform's only known data access point is through their DSA Single Point of Contact, with no dedicated research portal, APIs, dashboards, or formal application processes publicly documented. The absence of information extends to documentation quality, data dictionaries, codebooks, supplementary data availability, and volume restrictions, creating significant challenges for researchers attempting to study the platform. This limited transparency stands in contrast to other VLOPs' more structured research programs and raises questions about DSA compliance regarding data access requirements.

Focus on the Meta Content Library & API

The Meta Content Library (MCL) consists of two distinct but interrelated products: the MCL graphical user interface and the application programming interface.

Meta Content Library GUI

The MCL graphical user interface enables users to search indexed content across Facebook, Instagram, and Threads platforms (Tab. 1). This indexed content primarily includes posts shared by widely-viewed individuals and organizations. Users can apply various filters to refine their searches. Those familiar with CrowdTangle's Search feature will notice a strong similarity between these interfaces.

The two primary filtering options are platform selection and dataset type (see Fig. 1). Users can first choose which platform to search (Facebook, Instagram, or Threads). For Facebook and Instagram searches, users can then specify whether to access the view-only public dataset or the downloadable public data subset.

Fig. 1. The search interface of the Meta Content Library GUI

The MCL GUI features a tool that allows users to create, manage, and share collections of content producers from Facebook, Instagram, and Threads (similar to CrowdTangle's list management feature). Using the search interface, users can filter posts from single or multiple producer lists. Posts can be sorted by view count, chronological order, or reverse chronological order. However, sorting by likes/reactions, comments/replies, or shares/reposts is not available. Only posts that receive more than 100 views will display a view count. For posts created within the last 6 months, view counts are typically refreshed every 24 hours if the post receives more than 10 views within that period.

Component Type	Facebook	Instagram	Threads
Engagement Metrics			
Likes/Reactions	✓	✓	✓
Comments/Replies	✓	✓	✓
Shares/Reposts	✓	-	✓
Views	✓ (>100 views)	✓ (>100 views)	✓ (>100 views)
Media Types			
Text	✓	-	✓
Images	✓	✓	✓
Videos/Reels	✓	✓	✓
Links	✓	-	✓
Albums	-	✓	✓
Other Info			
Post Owner	✓	✓	✓
Post Date	✓	✓	✓
Surface Country	✓	-	-
Activity Type/Name	✓	-	-
View History			
Earliest Available	Jan 2017	Oct 2022	March 2024
Refresh Rate (<180 days)	24hrs if >10 views	24hrs if >10 views	24hrs if >10 views
Refresh Rate (>180 days)	5-7 days	3-5 days	Every 2 days

Tab. 1. Components of a post per platform

Additionally, the MCL GUI's dashboard feature lets users monitor specific keywords or accounts through a multi-column interface, reminiscent of Tweetdeck or CrowdTangle Live Displays. While these dashboards can be shared with other MCL users, they cannot currently be made public.

Meta Content Library API

The Meta Content Library (MCL) API is accessed through a clean room environment. Currently two approved environments exist: the Researcher Platform directly managed by Meta itself and the Virtual Data Enclave managed by the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) at the University of Michigan. The way the documentation is structured suggests that additional third-party cleanroom environments may be available in the future.

The Researcher Platform

The Researcher Platform is accessible via a VPN and consists of a customized version of Jupyter Notebook characterized by additional security measures such as disabled downloads and access to a limited list of pre-approved packages/libraries. To the best of our knowledge, this clean room environment is invite only, originally used by beta testers of the API and there is no currently available application process to access the API via this specific clean room environment. The Meta Content Library API available endpoints are extensively documented on a publicly available website maintained by Meta at <https://developers.facebook.com/docs/content-library-and-api/content-library-api>.

ICPSR Virtual Data Enclave (VDE) Cleanroom

The Virtual Data Enclave (VDE) was designed to allow researchers to access highly sensitive data remotely, eliminating the need to travel to a physical clean room.

To access the MCL API in this secure environment, researchers must:

- Create an account in the University of Michigan system
- Enable two-factor authentication
- Download and install VPN software
- Connect to a Windows virtual machine (VM) via remote desktop through the VPN
- Launch a Linux VM from within the Windows VM
- Connect to the Linux VM via remote desktop

The Linux VM operates in isolation from the internet, and copy/paste functionality is disabled. Multiple researchers from the same team share this VM, which comes pre-configured with both Python and R development environments. While researchers can install packages from official repositories (CRAN for R and PyPI for Python), any packages requiring internet connectivity will not function.

User documentation for third-party cleanroom interfaces is outside the scope of the Meta Content Library API documentation and it is instead provided by the third-party's system administrator. This means that the comprehensive and detailed documentation provided by Meta can't be directly used for third-party clear rooms. In the case of the VDE, the documentation consists of two documents (one for R and the other for python) that display the basic way to construct the queries for the different available endpoints.

Focus on the TikTok Research API

The TikTok Research API allows approved researchers to collect data on public TikTok videos, users, and comments. Unlike the Meta Content Library API, the TikTok Research API can be accessed directly from any internet-connected device, and the data can be stored locally for a limited time period for analysis. The public documentation also describes a secure computing environment called Virtual Compute Environment (VCE). However, it is unclear whether TikTok intends for the VCE to replace the open API or to serve as an additional channel for accessing more sensitive data (such as data requested by vetted researchers through the Digital Services Act's delegated channels).

Available Endpoints

The TikTok Research API has expanded from three to nine endpoints. The original endpoints consist of Video, Accounts, and Comments capabilities. The Video endpoint enables researchers to search for videos using various criteria such as keywords, hashtags, region codes, and timeframes. For matching videos, it returns comprehensive metadata including view counts, likes, comments, and shares. The Accounts endpoint provides detailed insights into user profiles, including information about followers, following lists, liked videos, pinned videos, and reposts. The Comments endpoint grants access to video comments data, though it's capped at 1,000 comments per post.

The API's expansion introduces six new endpoints. The User Liked Videos endpoint allows researchers to analyze public user preferences by accessing lists of liked videos along with their metadata, such as video IDs, descriptions, and engagement metrics. The User Pinned Videos endpoint reveals which content users choose to highlight on their profiles, offering insights into personal content curation and identity presentation.

For network analysis, the User Followers and User Following endpoints are particularly valuable. The Followers endpoint provides data about an account's followers and public metrics, enabling researchers to assess reach and influence. The Following endpoint reveals which accounts a user follows, helping researchers understand content preferences and map network connections.

The final two endpoints focus on content sharing and organization. The User Reposted Videos endpoint tracks which videos users choose to amplify, providing valuable data for studying content virality and sharing patterns. The Playlist Information endpoint gives researchers access to user-curated playlists, including titles and video contents, revealing how users organize and categorize content on the platform.

TikTok has also indicated plans to release an API for tracking content moderation actions, though this feature remains unavailable as of now.

Key Considerations When Using the TikTok Research API

Data Accuracy: Reports of inconsistencies between API metadata and TikTok's displayed data are a concern, particularly for research relying on precise metadata.

Exhaustiveness: The API does not return all publicly available videos. For instance, videos from deleted, suspended, or private accounts are excluded.

Rate Limits: Researchers are restricted to 1,000 requests per day, potentially hindering large-scale data collection efforts.

Data Management: The API terms require data refreshing every 15 days and sharing outputs with TikTok seven days before publication. This can be logistically demanding, especially for large datasets.

Limited Variables: The API offers access to a constrained set of variables, potentially restricting the scope of research questions.

Technical Support: The responsiveness of TikTok's technical support team has been inconsistent, with slow response times or missing responses to researcher queries. This impedes troubleshooting and creates delays in research projects when technical issues arise.

Challenges and Recommendations for Social Media Research in the DSA Era

The Digital Services Act (DSA) marks a significant shift in how digital platforms are regulated within the European Union. While the DSA aims to enhance transparency and accountability, researchers currently face several challenges when accessing and utilizing social media data and tools under Article 40.12. This chapter examines these challenges, followed by emerging opportunities, presented as action points, that could enhance research capabilities. Note that all tools and services discussed are actively being developed, and some challenges described may have been resolved by the time of publication. For the most current information, please refer to each platform's official documentation.

Challenges

While the DSA aims to enhance transparency and accountability, researchers currently face several challenges when accessing and utilizing social media data and tools under Article 40.12. This chapter examines these challenges, including issues with data quality, access restrictions, legal uncertainties, and their impact on different research communities.

Data Quality and Reliability

Researchers frequently encounter issues with inaccurate or incomplete metadata provided by platform APIs. Studies have highlighted discrepancies in the metadata returned by TikTok's API, raising concerns about data reliability. Furthermore, notable inconsistencies exist between data obtained via APIs and information visible on platforms' front-ends. These discrepancies can lead to misinterpretations and flawed analyses, underscoring the need for researchers to validate API data against other sources through manual verification.

Rate Limits and Data Volume Restrictions

Restrictive rate limits imposed by platforms hinder large-scale research projects, especially those requiring longitudinal data collection or analysis of extensive datasets. These limitations can impede comprehensive studies and affect the generalizability of research outcomes. Additionally, the lack of standardized rate limits across different platforms poses challenges for comparative research, complicating efforts to conduct cross-platform analyses and synthesize findings.

Ambiguity in the Definition of "Publicly Accessible Data"

The DSA lacks a clear definition of "publicly accessible data," leading to varying interpretations and potentially limited data access. In the absence of a standardized definition, platforms have discretion to determine what data they make available to researchers. This ambiguity can result in inconsistent data availability and challenges in determining the legality of data usage for research purposes.

Complex Application Processes

Researchers often face lengthy application review times for data access programs, which can delay research projects and hinder time-sensitive studies. Application processes typically require detailed research proposals, ethics committee approvals, and comprehensive data management plans. These requirements can be resource-intensive and may pose barriers, particularly for independent or early-career researchers. The lack of transparency in platform decision-making regarding application approvals leaves researchers uncertain about rejection reasons, potentially discouraging research initiatives.

Restrictive Terms and Conditions

Platforms often impose limitations on data retention and refresh periods, complicating longitudinal research or re-analysis over time. Terms requiring researchers to submit publications for platform review before dissemination raise concerns about research independence and academic freedom. These conditions can lead to censorship or undue influence over research findings.

Technical Barriers and Access Limitations

The reliance on technical expertise and coding skills for utilizing APIs limits accessibility for non-technical researchers, potentially excluding valuable perspectives and reducing research approach diversity. Civil society organizations often face limited access to research programs and APIs, despite their crucial role in monitoring platform activity and advocating for policy changes. This restriction negatively impacts public interest research, limiting the ability to study content moderation practices and their societal implications.

While these challenges present significant obstacles for researchers and civil society organizations, they also highlight crucial opportunities for improvement in the current framework. The identification of these specific barriers enables targeted solutions and policy recommendations to enhance data access,

standardize procedures, and promote more inclusive research environments. The following section outlines concrete recommendations to address these challenges and strengthen the research ecosystem under Article 40.12 of the DSA.

Recommendations

Clearer Regulatory Frameworks and Guidance

The current ambiguities in the DSA present an opportunity to establish more explicit guidelines for research. A refined legal definition of "publicly accessible data" would ensure consistent interpretations across platforms and provide researchers with clear boundaries for lawful data collection. This clarification would help distinguish between two key data access mechanisms established in Article 40: the real-time APIs for publicly accessible data (Article 40(12)), and the vetted researcher access to private data governed by this delegated regulation (Article 40(4)). Similarly, standardizing application procedures for data access programs could promote efficiency and equity. A unified approach would establish consistent timelines and transparent decision-making criteria, ensuring fair access across institutions and researcher demographics, particularly benefiting early-career researchers and underfunded organizations.

Standardization of APIs and Data Formats

The development of standardized APIs and data formats could significantly enhance cross-platform research capabilities. By adopting shared technical standards, platforms can enable researchers to analyze online phenomena across multiple platforms, providing a more comprehensive understanding of digital behaviors. The real-time APIs mandated by the DSA should be openly accessible via secure HTTPS connections, without requiring virtual clean rooms or other restricted environments given the public nature of the data. Critically, these APIs must include direct links to the original content on the platforms. This requirement serves two essential purposes: it enables easy verification and reporting of findings (researchers can readily share specific cases with others) and helps ensure data reliability (API data can be cross-referenced with what users see on the platform interface). This standardization would facilitate the development of interoperable tools and foster collaboration among researchers studying topics such as misinformation, content moderation, and network behaviors. Such standardization would also enable third-party developers to create research tools and software that can seamlessly interact with data across platforms, reducing technical barriers and democratizing access to platform data analysis. These tools could range from data collection utilities and visualization frameworks to advanced analytical software, all building upon the common standards established by the DSA's data access framework.

Enhanced Research Tools and Support

Platforms could develop user-friendly dashboards with built-in filtering, visualization, and analytic functionalities to democratize access for non-technical researchers. Comprehensive documentation, including detailed data dictionaries and codebooks, would improve researchers' ability to effectively use available tools. Dedicated and responsive support teams could assist researchers with technical issues, help resolve API-related challenges, and provide timely guidance on terms of service and compliance

requirements. These support teams should maintain clear communication channels and commit to specific response times, ensuring that research projects aren't delayed by technical obstacles or pending clarifications about data access procedures.

Expanded Data Access and Volume

Platforms could enhance research capabilities by implementing more flexible access tiers based on project needs. This approach would support various research scenarios, from exploratory studies requiring limited data samples to comprehensive analyses needing long-term, high-volume access. Increased rate limits for academic and public interest research would enable more robust studies while maintaining platform infrastructure stability.

Independent Data Quality Assessment

The establishment of an independent entity for data quality testing could significantly improve research reliability. Regular audits by trusted third parties would help detect discrepancies in API outputs, build confidence in data integrity, and provide platforms with recommendations for improvement. This independent oversight would strengthen the credibility of research findings and support evidence-based policymaking.

Civil Society Research Integration

Expanding access for civil society researchers would strengthen the research ecosystem's ability to address societal challenges. Civil society organizations bring unique perspectives to studying content moderation practices, systemic risks, and online harms. Providing them with equivalent access to research tools would foster collaboration between academic institutions and advocacy groups, ensuring that public interest priorities are adequately represented in research agendas.

Building a Community of DSA Research Data and Tool Users

The European Union should take an active role in establishing and maintaining a community of researchers using platform-provided tools under the DSA framework. A crucial first step is simply connecting researchers who have been granted access to different platforms' tools and data, enabling them to share experiences, challenges, and solutions. This basic networking function would help prevent researchers from working in isolation and facilitate the sharing of practical knowledge. The Facebook/Social Science One incident of 2021³⁰, where a major data error affected numerous academic studies, demonstrates why such community interaction is crucial. Like those tools, the DSA's new research APIs and interfaces will require extensive real-world testing to identify bugs, reliability issues, and data quality problems. The European Commission, through its Joint Research Centre (JRC) or dedicated DSA oversight bodies, should coordinate this community-building effort by maintaining a

³⁰ <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2021/09/10/facebook-error-data-social-scientists/> and <https://www.nytimes.com/live/2020/2020-election-misinformation-distortions#facebook-sent-flawed-data-to-misinformation-researchers>.

directory of vetted researchers and organizing regular opportunities for them to connect. Beyond just identifying technical issues, this community would help validate data quality and completeness.

To build and sustain such a community, the EU should create formal mechanisms for researcher engagement, such as an official working group or research network. This structure would help ensure diverse research applications across multiple disciplines while also providing collective expertise to spot potential data anomalies early. The community should include researchers from various fields, each bringing unique perspectives on data quality and methodological approaches.

The EU should facilitate regular forums for user feedback, including workshops, online discussions, and collaborative documentation efforts. These events would create a continuous feedback loop between platforms, researchers, and regulators - something that was notably missing in the Facebook case until researchers independently discovered the data issues. This interaction would help ensure tools evolve in alignment with both research needs and regulatory objectives.

Beyond this White Paper

The information in this report is accurate as of the publication date. However, readers should consult official documentation provided by the VLOPs and VLOSEs for the most recent developments.

Recognizing the need for a comprehensive resource on social media research APIs and tools in the Digital Services Act era, we have developed an interactive AI chatbot as an online extension of this white paper.

The prototype is available to the public at 40point12.eu.

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